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Active Region Classification and Flare Forecasting

ARCAFF

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the deliverable

The ARCAFF project develops several Deep Learning (DL) models for the classification, localisation and forecasting of solar flares. To provide robust, scalable, portable and easily accessible solutions, ARCAFF creates containerised cloud-based services from these models and offers them to the wider community through a publicly available web portal, called the PITHIA e-Science Centre (PeSC)¹. The PeSC has been developed in the EU funded PITHIA-NRF project² by the University of Westminster team to support the plasmasphere, ionosphere and thermosphere research communities in Europe and beyond to access their data collections and execute computational models on demand. As the ARCAFF services align well with the PITHIA research domain, it has been an objective of ARCAFF from the beginning to publish all developed Deep Learning models in the PeSC and make these easily accessible and executable by the wider community.

This deliverable describes the activities in the first half of project related to the containerisation of the ARCAFF DL services, setting up these services in a cloud computing infrastructure offered and operated by SZTAKI, developing and publishing an Application Programming Interface (API) to provide remote access to the services, and registering and offering the DL models in the PeSC through the developed APIs.

Although at this stage of the project no DL models have been fully completed and operational, a classification model has already been implemented and offered in the PeSC. While this model does not fully provide the functionalities of the final DL model, its interface and the required metadata for publication are the same as in the case of the final model. Therefore, deploying this model in a container, developing and offering its API and publishing it in the PeSC are also identical as in case of the final model and will not require any (major) modification as the model develops. Additionally, it provides us with a template and methodology on how future DL models will be deployed and published in the PeSC.

The rest of this deliverable describes the work that was carried out when containerising and deploying the model in the Cloud and publishing it in the PeSC.

¹ Gabriele Pierantoni, Tamas Kiss, Alexander Bolotov, Dimitrios Kagialis, James DesLauriers, Amjad Ullah, Huankai Chen, David Chan You Fee, Hai-Van Dang, Jozsef Kovacs, Anna Belehaki, Themistocles Herekakis, Ioanna Tsagouri, Sandra Gesing: Towards a Reference Architecture based Science Gateway Framework with Embedded E-Learning Support, Concurrency and Computation, Practice and Experience, Wiley, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cpe.6872>.

² PITHIA-NRF EU-funded project - <https://pithia-nrf.eu/>

1.2 References

ID	Title
D2.1	Data Management Plan
D2.2	AR Localisation and Classification ML Datasets
D3.1	Trained AR Localisation and Classification DNNs

1.3 Acronyms

Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Active Region
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph
DL	Deep Learning
HMI	Helioseismic and Magnetic Imager
HTML	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IaaS	Infrastructure As a Service
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MDI	Michelson Doppler Imager
PaaS	Platform As a Service
PeSC	Pithia e-Science Centre
PITHIA-NRF	Plasmasphere Ionosphere Thermosphere Integrated Research Environment and Access services: a Network of Research Facilities
QS	Quiet Sun

R-CNN	Region-based Convolutional Neural Network
ResNet	Residual Neural Network
REST	Representational State Transfer
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
ViTs	Vision Transformers
VM	Virtual Machine
XML	Extensible Markup Language
YOLO	You Only Look Once

2. Report Deliverable

2.1 The ARCAFF DL Models

The ARCAFF Deep Learning Models and data are thoroughly described in their respective deliverables D2.2 and D3.1, for context a short synopsis of the models is provided below. The ARCAFF DL models are distinguished based on their specific tasks: AR Cutout Classification and AR Detection.

AR Cutout Classification Models: these models classify cutouts of magnetograms taken by either the HMI or the MDI. The input magnetogram cutout undergoes a series of preprocessing steps before being categorised into the classes QS, plage regions, Alpha, Beta, and Beta-Gamma. The available trained models include ResNet variants and ViTs of different sizes.

AR Detection: These models take as input an HMI or MDI full disk magnetogram. First, ARs are localised within the solar disk and a bounding box for each of them is found, subsequently, the detected ARs are classified into either Alpha, Beta, or Beta-Gamma classes. The trained models belong to the YOLO family and Faster R-CNN models and are hosted on Comet³

The DL models are wrapped in a FastAPI⁴ API which provides a RESTlike HTTP interface and documentation to run the models with the required inputs. Figures 1 and 2 below show examples of accessing the models via the API from the command line using the HTTP protocol.

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'http://127.0.0.1:8000/arcnet/classify_cutout/' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \ -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{ "time": "2022-11-12T13:14:15+00:00",
      "hgs_latitude": 0, "hgs_longitude": 0 }'
{ "time": "2022-11-12T13:14:15Z", "hgs_latitude": 0, "hgs_longitude": 0,
  "hale_class": "QS", "mcintosh_class": "QS"}
```

Figure 1 - Example HTTP access of AR Cutout classification model

³ Comet - <https://www.comet.com/site/>

⁴ FastAPI - <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>

```
curl -X 'POST' \
  'http://127.0.0.1:8000/arcnet/full_disk_detection' \
  -H 'accept: application/json' \
  -H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
  -d '{ "time": "2022-11-12T13:14:15+00:00" }'

[{"time": "2022-11-12T13:14:15Z",
  "bbox": {
    "bottom_left": {
      "latitude": 20, "longitude": 18 },
    "top_right": { "latitude": 30, "longitude": 28 } },
  "hale_class": "Beta", "mcintosh_class": "Dao"},
{"time": "2022-11-12T13:14:15Z",
  "bbox": {
    "bottom_left": {"latitude": 9, "longitude": 9 },
    "top_right": { "latitude": 19, "longitude": 19 } },
  "hale_class": "Beta-Gamma-Delta", "mcintosh_class": "Eki" },
{"time": "2022-11-12T13:14:15Z",
  "bbox": {
    "bottom_left": { "latitude": 22, "longitude": 3 },
    "top_right": {"latitude": 32, "longitude": 13 } },
  "hale_class": "Alpha", "mcintosh_class": "Axx"}]
```

Figure 2 - Example showing HTTP access of the AR Detection model.

2.2 API Development and Deployment

As the actual ARCAFF models are under development, as a first step a representative “mock” API has been developed and published. DIAS provided the presented “mock” API (<https://github.com/ARCAFF/fapi>) with a Dockerfile suitable for creating a Docker image for the API deployment. The created image was built from a python:3.11 base image containing the API's source code with the necessary installed dependencies. After the container creation, the API will start automatically and listen to the 80 TCP port by default.

To deploy the Docker image, SZTAKI created a dedicated ARCAFF project on the HUN-REN Cloud⁵. Based on OpenStack operated by HUN-REN SZTAKI and HUN-REN Wigner FK, this Hungarian scientific cloud provides IaaS and PaaS-level service for Hungarian and European researchers and research projects. The ARCAFF Cloud project comprises three virtual machines (VMs) with 16 vCPU cores, 32GB RAM, and 512GB SSD-based storage, as shown in Figures 3 and 4.

⁵ HUN-REN Cloud - <https://science-cloud.hu/en>

Figure 3 - HUN-REN Cloud ARCAFF project resources

Instances

Displaying 3 items

Instance Name	Image Name	IP Address	Flavor	Key Pair	Status	Availability Zone	Task	Power State	Age	Actions
monitoring-server	Ubuntu 22.04 LTS	192.168.0.162	m2.large	kpora	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	2 days, 19 hours	Create Snapshot
Proxy	Ubuntu 24.04 [20240912]	192.168.0.73, 193.225.251.163	m2.large	emodi	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	1 month	Create Snapshot
arcaff-service	Ubuntu 22.04 LTS	192.168.0.149	m2.xlarge	farkas	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	9 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot

Displaying 3 items

Figure 4 - ARCAFF virtual machines

The “arcaff-service” VM with 8 vCPU cores and 16GB RAM is used to deploy the previously introduced API Docker container as a service, presented in Figure 5.

```
ubuntu@arcaff-service:~$ docker ps -a
```

CONTAINER ID	IMAGE	COMMAND	CREATED	STATUS	PORTS	NAMES
67ce85cf35d3	consul:1.14.3	"docker-entrypoint.s..."	2 days ago	Up 2 days		consul_agent
e87a69232a53	gcr.io/cadvisor/cadvisor:v0.46.0	"/usr/bin/cadvisor -..."	2 days ago	Up 2 days (unhealthy)		cadvisor
24fa313fe668	prom/node-exporter:v1.5.0	"/bin/node_exporter ..."	2 days ago	Up 2 days		node-exporter
e0d79803e3f8	arcaff-api:0.1.0	"unicorn app.main.ap..."	9 months ago	Up 4 weeks	0.0.0.0:8000->80/tcp, :::8000->80/tcp	arcaff-api

Figure 5 - ARCAFF containers

The Proxy VM with 4vCPU and 8GB RAM deploys a Cady HTTP proxy to make the API publicly available. The Cady VM has a public IP address and the “arcaff.sztaki.hun-ren.hu” domain name. The HTTP proxy provided HTTPS termination for secure communication on the public Internet. Furthermore, the Cady HTTP proxy provides an HTTP header-based filtering process. The presented PITHIA e-Science Centre in the upcoming section calls the model APIs from various IP addresses but with a specific HTTP header. Therefore, we can filter and accept only those HTTP calls towards our API containing the specific HTTP header. This filtering process is presented in Figure 6.

```
→ ~ curl -X 'POST' \
'https://arcaff.sztaki.hun-ren.hu/arcnet/classify_cutout/' \
-H 'accept: application/json' \
-H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
-H "Origin: esc.pithia.eu" \
-d '{
  "time": "2022-11-12T13:14:15+00:00",
  "hgs_latitude": 0,
  "hgs_longitude": 0
}'
{"time":"2022-11-12T13:14:15Z","hgs_latitude":0.0,"hgs_longitude":0.0,"hale_class":"QS","mcintosh_class":"QS"}
→ ~ curl -X 'POST' \
'https://arcaff.sztaki.hun-ren.hu/arcnet/classify_cutout/' \
-H 'accept: application/json' \
-H 'Content-Type: application/json' \
-d '{
  "time": "2022-11-12T13:14:15+00:00",
  "hgs_latitude": 0,
  "hgs_longitude": 0
}'
Forbidden!
```

Figure 6 - ARCAFF HTTP Proxy filtering

The monitoring-server VM with 4vCPU and 8GB RAM provided a Prometheus and Grafana-based monitoring solution. We deployed the monitoring stack as Docker containers on the monitoring node and added several exporters to the observed VMs. We use the Node exporter to collect VM-level metrics, cAdvisor to collect container-based information, and the Cady proxy to provide Prometheus-compatible metrics by default. We monitor the resource usage presented in Figure 7 and the number of API calls presented in Figure 8 via these metrics.

Figure 7 - ARCAFF deployment resource monitoring

Figure 8 - ARCAFF Proxy API monitoring

The HUN-REN Cloud deployment is prepared to serve the real ARCAFF model when it is production-ready. With the monitoring system, we can observe the whole deployment, and if necessary, now or with the final model, we can scale up the API to meet user needs. Based

on the collected metrics, we will investigate the possibility of using a multi-level auto-scaling platform like MiCADO⁶.

2.3 Publishing the ARCAFF Model in the PITHIA e-Science Centre

Publishing the ARCAFF DL models in the PITHIA e-Science Centre requires the completion of five steps:

1. Model owners/developers must register in the PeSC.
2. An ARCAFF Institution must be created in the PeSC.
3. Model owners/developers must join the ARCAFF institution.
4. Scientific metadata (in XML format) describing the model must be published in the PeSC under the ARCAFF Institution.
5. The Model API must be registered as an interaction method with the model.

The PITHIA e-Science Centre realises the above five steps through its user management system (utilising EGI Check-in⁷ and Perun⁸ services), where scientists can authenticate and authorise themselves to publish scientific metadata on behalf of any research/academic institution they are a member of.

The following subsections highlight the background work related to the PeSC and the ARCAFF AR Classification Model deployment details.

2.3.1 The PITHIA e-Science Centre

PITHIA-NRF (Plasmasphere Ionosphere Thermosphere Integrated Research Environment and Access services: a Network of Research Facilities) is a four-year project funded by the European Commission's H2020 programme to integrate data, models and physical observing facilities for further advancing European research capacity in this area. A central point of PITHIA-NRF is the PITHIA e-Science Centre (PeSC), a science gateway that provides access to distributed data sources and prediction models to support scientific discovery.

⁶ MiCADO - <https://micado-scale.eu>

⁷ EGI Checkin - <https://aai.eqi.eu/registry/>

⁸ EGI Perun - <https://perun.eqi.eu/>

Figure 9 - Main screen of the PeSC with a user logged in to the ARCAFF Institution

One of the main objectives of the PeSC is to enable scientists to register their Data Collections, that can be both raw or higher-level datasets and prediction models, using a standard metadata format and a domain ontology. For these purposes, PITHIA builds on the results of the ESPAS FP7 project⁹ by adopting and modifying its ontology and metadata specification. The project utilises the ISO 19156 standard on Observations and Measurements (O&M) to describe Data Collections in an XML format that is widely used within the research community. Following the standard, Data Collections are referring to other XML documents, such as Computations that a model used to derive the results, Acquisitions describing how the data

⁹ Anna Belehaki, Sarah James, Mike Hapgood, Spiros Ventouras, Ivan Galkin, Antonis Lembesis, Ioanna Tzagouri, Anna Charisi, Luca Spogli, Jens Berdermann, Ingemar Häggström, The ESPAS e-infrastructure: Access to data from near-Earth space, *Advances in Space Research*, Volume 58, Issue 7, 2016, Pages 1177-1200, ISSN 0273-1177, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2016.06.014>.

was collected, Instruments that were used during the data collection process, or Projects that were responsible for the data/model. Within the XML documents, specific keywords of the Space Physics ontology can be used to describe the various elements. For example, Observed Property can be Field, Particle, Wave, or Mixed, at the top level. When preparing the XML metadata file, only these values are accepted for validation. Once described in XML format, Data Collections can be published in the PeSC and searched using the ontology-based search engine.

Besides large and typically changing/growing Data Collections, PeSC also supports the registration of Catalogues. These are smaller sets of data, originating from a Data Collection and related to specific events, e.g. volcano eruptions. Catalogue Data Subsets can be assigned DOIs to be referenced in publications and provide a permanent set of data for reproducibility.

Finally, Workflows can also be registered in the PeSC. A workflow is a combination of different interconnected Data Collections executed repeatedly in an orchestrated pattern to produce its output result. The pattern in its general form is a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) and in its simplest form, a linear sequence of steps.

Besides publication and search, the PeSC also provides several mechanisms for interacting with Data Collections, e.g. executing a model or downloading subsets of the data. In the current version two interaction methods are implemented: accessing the Data Collection by a direct link and interacting with it via an API and an automatically generated GUI. This second mechanism will be applied for ARCAFF models in the PeSC. Data Collections can either be hosted by the local provider or can be deployed on EGI cloud computing resources.

Accessing and downloading data and executing models in the PeSC is completely open and does not require any registration (the PeSC can be reached at <https://esc.pithia.eu/>). However, registering new Data Collections or managing existing ones requires the user to register and belong to an Institution within the PeSC. Once registered, users can publish new Data Collections within their Institution or modify and delete existing ones (also within their Institution only).

The main screen of the PeSC is illustrated in Figure 9. The particular user using this screen has already registered and logged in to the ARCAFF Institution and can edit all Data Collections registered there (details are described below in Sections 2.3.2 - 2.3.7). More information is available about the PeSC on the PITHIA-NRF¹⁰ project website. The PeSC source code is open and available on GitHub.

2.3.2 User Registration with the PeSC

Before creating the ARCAFF institution and publishing the ARCAFF DL Models, users must register with the PITHIA e-Science Centre by selecting the “Provider Login/Sign up” option at the upper right corner of the landing page, Figure 10.

¹⁰ PITHIA-NRF - <https://pithia-nrf.eu/>

Figure 10 - Landing Page of the PeSC where a Provider can log in/Sign Up

The “Provider Login/Sign up” option redirects the users to the EGI Check-in login page, which asks for the academic or cloud provider account (e.g. Google, LinkedIn) they would like to log in with, Figure 11. If a user is already registered, the EGI Check-in takes them back to the PeSC; otherwise, it takes them through the registration process, where they must accept EGI and PITHIA communities policies.

Figure 12 displays the PITHIA community policy. By selecting “Yes”, the user is now logged in to the PeSC for the first time and will be presented with the main page, as shown in Figure 13, with a request to “Join an Existing Institution” or “Register a New Institution”.

Check-in

Choose your academic/social account

Search...

- 29 Mayis University
- A*STAR - Agency for Science, Technology and Research
- A. T. Still University
- AAF Virtual Home
- abi.lab.meeen.sa
- AAI@EduHr Single Sign-On Service
- Aalborg University
- Aalto University
- Aarhus School of Architecture
- Aarhus School of Marine and Technical Engineering
- Aarhus University
- AARNet
- Aba Teachers University
- ABC - Academia Brasileira de Ciencias
- Abertay University
- Aberystwyth University
- ABES - French Bibliographic Agency for Higher Education

or

Can't find your identity provider?

Figure 11 - PITHIA e-Science Centre EGI Check-in Login Account

Grant Access to Pithia e-Science Centre

This service requests the following permissions:

- **View your rights to resources**
- **View your basic profile info**
- **View your email address**

The service is based in: France

Make sure you trust Pithia e-Science Centre by learning how it will handle your data. Please read the [Privacy Policy](#) of the service provider. Please review the [Acceptable Use Policy](#).

Description provided by the service: PITHIA, Plasmasphere Ionosphere Thermosphere Integrated Research Environment and Access services, aims to integrate data, models and physical observing facilities for further advancing European research capacity in this area. A central point of PITHIA is the PITHIA e-Science Centre that provides access to distributed data sources and prediction models to support scientific discovery. The e-Science Centre enables scientist to access Data Collections (datasets or models) from one single entry point, find them based on a rich set of metadata and interact (download and analyse data, run prediction models) with them through graphical user interfaces.

[Additional information about the service](#)

Contacts: yin.chen@egi.eu, levente.farkas@egi.eu

You can revoke access from the [Applications dashboard](#)

Yes

No

Figure 12 - PITHIA e-Science Centre Policies

PITHIA e-Science Centre

You must be a member of an e-Science Centre institution to enable content management features for this account.

[Join an Existing Institution](#)

[Register a New Institution](#)

Figure 13 - PITHIA e-Science Centre Initial Login

2.3.3 Creating an ARCAFF Institution within the PeSC

Having registered as a user to the PeSC, an ARCAFF scientific member can use the “Register a New Institution” option, as shown in Figure 13, to create the ARCAFF institution within the PeSC.

The “Register a New Institution” option redirected the ARCAFF member to the EGI Perun, asking them to complete the application form by providing an institution name, description, and purpose, Figure 14.

Once the ARCAFF member submitted the request, the Global PeSC admin can approve it, resulting in the creation of a new ARCAFF institution within the PeSC. The user who requested the creation became its first Admin. Now, PeSC users can join the ARCAFF institution and publish scientific metadata managed by the institution.

Request to create a new institution

Placeholder for custom text or instructions.

Organization name*

Only a-z, A-Z, 0-9, dashes, underscores and spaces are allowed.

Organization description*

Description of organization within the management system. It is visible to both organization managers and members.

Organization purpose*

Please fill in the reason for organization creation and its expected purpose.

[Request a new organisation](#)

Figure 14 - PITHIA e-Science Centre Creation of a New Institution

2.3.4 Joining the ARCAFF Institution

To join the ARCAFF institution, the rest of the ARCAFF members can select “Join an Existing Institution”, Figure 13, and click on join the ARCAFF institution, which is displayed as the first option in Figure 15. There, the users had to choose between becoming an Admin or a Member of the institution, and the ARCAFF admin, after receiving an email notification can accept/decline the request. The difference between Admin and Member rights is that Admins receive and approve membership requests for the ARCAFF institution.

Join an Institution

ARCAFF - Active Region Classification and Flare Forecasting
Astron
Borealis Global Designs
Centre National d Etudes Spatiales
Centrum Badan Kosmicznych Polskiej Akademii Nauk
EISCAT Scientific Association
Ebro Observatory

Figure 15 - PITHIA e-Science Centre Join an Institution

2.3.6 Registering the ARCAFF DL Models within the PeSC

To register the ARCAFF DL models within the PeSC, the ARCAFF institution members logged in to the portal and selected to manage metadata for the ARCAFF institution. In Figure 16, under the Data Registration section, there are three options:

- Data Resource Registration Guide, where ARCAFF members consulted on how to build their metadata structure.
- Manage Registration, where ARCAFF members used to register ARCAFF DL model-related metadata.
- Metadata Models, where ARCAFF members found information related to the metadata schema.

The Manage Registration option permits users to manage metadata for Data Collections, Catalogues, and Workflows. Currently, the ARCAFF project utilises only Data Collection-related metadata, and Figure 17 displays already registered ARCAFF metadata. At the bottom, one Data Collection represents the registration of the ARCAFF AR Classification Model.

esc.pithia.eu

Space Physics Ontology Space Physics Ontology Guide

ARCAFF - Active Region Classification and Flare Forecasting

Data Registration

Data Resource Registration Guide Manage Registrations Metadata Models

Figure 16 - PITHIA e-Science Centre Data Registration

esc.pithia.eu/authorised/manage/data-collection-related-metadata/

Search Data Collections Scientific Metadata Space Physics Ontology

Home > Manage Registrations

Data Collection-related Metadata

Registering a data collection involves registering **up to 12 types of metadata**, registered in the order presented below. Information on what to include for each type can be found in the [data resource registration guide](#).

1.	Organisations 1
2.	Individuals 2
3.	Projects 1
4.	Platforms 0
5.	Operations 0
6.	Instruments 0
7.	Acquisition Capabilities 0
8.	Acquisitions 0
9.	Computation Capabilities 1
10.	Computations 1
11.	Processes 1
12.	Data Collections 1

Figure 17 - PITHIA e-Science Centre ARCAFF Data Collection-related Metadata

Figures 18, 19, and 20 demonstrate Data Collection-related metadata for Organisations, Individuals, and Projects. All types of metadata include a table with two columns, Name and Updated By, listing the available registrations. All views offer the same metadata management interface for registering new, updating, or deleting metadata.

There is also an option to view the XML file related to the registration, like in Figure 21, which displays the registration of the ARCAFF Project metadata.

The screenshot shows the 'Organisations' page in the PITHIA e-Science Centre ARCAFF system. The browser address bar is 'esc.pithia.eu/authorised/manage/organisations/'. The page header includes the PITHIA e-Science Centre logo and navigation links for 'Search Data Collections', 'Scientific Metadata', and 'Space Physics'. The breadcrumb trail is 'Home > Manage Registrations > Data Collection-related Metadata'. The main heading is 'Organisations', followed by a description: 'Data Provider/Owner organisation.' Below this are two buttons: 'Register via File Upload' and '+ Register with Wizard'. A table lists the following data:

Name	Updated by
Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies Organisation_DIAS, pithia	Shane Maloney

Figure 18 - PITHIA e-Science Centre ARCAFF Organisation Metadata

The screenshot shows the 'Individuals' page in the PITHIA e-Science Centre ARCAFF system. The browser address bar is 'esc.pithia.eu/authorised/manage/individuals/'. The page header includes the PITHIA e-Science Centre logo and navigation links for 'Search Data Collections', 'Scientific Metadata', and 'Space Physics Ont'. The breadcrumb trail is 'Home > Manage Registrations > Data Collection-related Metadata'. The main heading is 'Individuals', followed by a description: 'An individual, acting in a particular role and associated with an Organisation.' Below this are two buttons: 'Register via File Upload' and '+ Register with Wizard'. A table lists the following data:

Name	Updated by
Paul Wright Individual_Paul_Wright, dias	Paul Wright
Shane Maloney Individual_Shane_Maloney, dias	Shane Maloney

Figure 19 - PITHIA e-Science Centre ARCAFF Individuals Metadata

esc.pithia.eu/authorised/manage/projects/

PITHIA e-Science Centre

Search Data Collections Scientific Metadata Space Physics Ont

Home > Manage Registrations > Data Collection-related Metadata

Projects

An identifiable activity designed to accomplish a set of objectives.

Register via File Upload + Register with Wizard

Name	Updated by
Active Region Classification and Flare Forecasting Project_Active_Region_Classification_And_Flare_Forecasting, dias	Shane Maloney

Figure 20 - PITHIA e-Science Centre ARCAFF Projects Metadata

esc.pithia.eu/projects/Project_Active_Region_Classification_And_Flare_Forecasting/xml/

Active Region Classification and Flare Forecasting [Download]

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<Project xmlns="https://metadata.pithia.eu/schemas/2.2" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  <identifier>
    <PITHIA_Identifier>
      <localID>Project_Active_Region_Classification_And_Flare_Forecasting</localID>
      <namespace>dias</namespace>
      <version>1</version>
      <creationDate>2024-06-26T00:00:00Z</creationDate>
      <lastModificationDate>2024-06-26T00:00:00Z</lastModificationDate>
    </PITHIA_Identifier>
  </identifier>
  <name>Active Region Classification and Flare Forecasting</name>
  <shortName>ARCAFF</shortName>
  <abstract>The Sun is an enigmatic star that produces the most powerful explosive events in our solar system. The large amount of available space-based solar observations are an ideal candidate for this type of analysis. ARCAFF will increase the accuracy and timeliness of current operational flare forecast products and create new products. The five key objectives of ARCAFF are:
  <ol>
    <li>1. Active region classifications using magnetogram cutouts</li>
    <li>2. Active region localisation and classification using full disk magnetograms</li>
    <li>3. Point-in-time flare prediction using full disk magnetograms</li>
    <li>4. Point-in-time flare prediction using full disk multimodal observations</li>
    <li>5. Time series flare prediction based on time series of full disk multimodal observations</li>
  </ol>
  </abstract>
  <description/>
  <URL>
    <gmd:URL>https://arcaff.eu</gmd:URL>
  </URL>
  <status xlink:href="https://metadata.pithia.eu/ontology/2.2/status/OnGoing"/>
</Project>
```

Figure 21 - PITHIA e-Science Centre ARCAFF Project Metadata XML File

Registering the related Data Collection was the last step of the registration process, and it was performed through the registration wizard, as shown in Figure 22. Finally, Figure 23 displays the Data Collection of the ARCAFF AR Classification Model, now publicly available to all PeSC users.

Search Data Collections Scientific Metadata Space Physics Ontology

Home > Manage Registrations > Data Collection-related Metadata > Data Collections

Metadata Sections

- Full Name and Organisation
- Identifier
- Description, Types, Features of Interest and Permissions
- Projects, Procedure and Sub-collections
- Collection Results
- Data Levels
- Quality Assessment
- Related Parties

Data Collection Wizard

* indicates a required field

Data Collection Full Name *

Activity Indicator: Solar Active Region Classification

Identifier

Metadata Version *

The version number of the object being identified.

1

Figure 22 - PITHIA e-Science Centre ARCAFF Data Collection Registration Wizard

Data Collections

Top-level definition of a collection of the model c
CollectionResults pointing to its URL(s) for acce
Catalogues, data collections do not include begi

Register via File Upload

+ Register with

Name

Activity Indicator: Solar Active Region
Classification

DataCollection_Activity_Indicator_Solar_Active_Region
_Classification, dias

Figure 23 - PITHIA e-Science Centre ARCAFF Data Collections Metadata

2.3.7 Registering the ARCAFF DL Model API

Despite the fact that the ARCAFF Data Collection is registered, as shown in Figure 23, assigning the API to the Data Collection was necessary to allow users to interact with the ARCAFF AR Classification Model API. To do so, next to the registered Data Collection table, there is an “Update Interaction Methods” option, which loads the view of Figure 24. There, by enabling the “API” checkbox and adding under the “OpenAPI Specification URL” textbox the URL of the API specification file, a validation is performed. Once done, the user saves the changes, and the eSC enables access to the Data Collection through that API.

pithia.eu/authorised/data-collections/DataCollection_Activity_Indicator_Solar_Active_Region_Classification/update/interaction-methods

[Home](#) > [Manage Registrations](#) > [Data Collection-related Metadata](#) > [Data Collections](#)

Update Interaction Methods

Activity Indicator: Solar Active Region Classification

i Select and fill out the interaction method details you would like to add for **Activity Indicator: Solar Active Region Classification** below, then click **Save** to save your changes.

Link to Data Collection (added inside the XML Metadata File)
If a URL is put inside a `<linkage>` element, this will be provided as a direct link to the Data Collection.

API
A link to an OpenAPI specification (written in YAML or JSON) for interacting with the Data Collection can be provided below. A user interface will be generated from this specification and will be accessible from the details page of the Data Collection in the e-Science Centre.

OpenAPI Specification URL

Description

Figure 24 - PITHIA e-Science Centre ARCAFF Data Collections Metadata

2.4 Using the Model

The previous section was about registering the DL Model, specifically the ARCAFF AR Classification Model and its API, within the PeSC, and this section demonstrates how PeSC users can utilise its API through the PeSC.

At the top of the landing page, the PeSC users see the “Scientific Metadata” section, as shown in Figure 25. This section is available to the public with open access, and the fastest way to see the available Data Collections is by selecting the “Data Collections” option. This opens a view listing all Data Collections grouped by their purpose, Figure 26.

Figure 25 - PITHIA e-Science Centre Open Access to Scientific Metadata

At the bottom of Figure 26, under the Computation Models, users can find the “Solar Active Region Classification” model registered by the ARCAFF institution. By selecting this Data Collection, users are redirected to a view with details of the Data Collection, like its description and related Individuals and Projects, Figure 27, details that come directly from the registered metadata, like Individuals and Projects, Figures 18,19.

Data Collections

Top-level definition of a collection of the model or measurement data, with CollectionResults pointing to its URL(s) for accessing the data. Unlike [Catalogues](#), data collections do not include begin and end times.

61 Data Collections

Activity Indicators

EIS current ionospheric conditions at each ionosonde location
Hp30 and ap30 indices
Hp60 and ap60 indices
Kp, ap, and Ap indices, F10.7 radio flux and sunspot number
PCN (Polar Cap North) index
TechTIDE LSTID activity index
T-FORS MSTID Climatology

Sensor Measurements

AWDA VLF collection of Equatorial Electron Density in the Plasmasphere
DIDBase: Digital Ionogram DataBase, autoscaled records
DIDBase: Digital Ionogram DataBase, manually scaled records
EISCAT Svalbard Dynasonde analysed data
EISCAT Svalbard Radar Data in the Madrigal Database
EISCAT Tromsø Dynasonde analysed data
EISCAT UHF Radar Data in the Madrigal Database
EISCAT UHF Radar Vector Data in the Madrigal Database
Show all 23 sensor measurements...

Computational Models

Activity Indicator: Solar Active Region Classification
BOB1_qModel

Figure 26 - ARCAFF Data Collection Solar Active Region Classification under Computational Models

Activity Indicator: Solar Active Region Classification

Last modified at Sep 24th, 2024, 13:47 GMT

Solar Active Region Classification

Principal Investigator

[Shane Maloney](#)

Access this Data Collection

with the PITHIA e-Science Centre

[Go to API](#) →

Description

ARCAFF is a classification model that identifies and classifies presence of the active regions on solar magnetogram from NOAA. ARCAFF runs on demand to take the user-defined date and time and then locate the matching NOAA magnetogram to interpret it automatically.

Permissions

▶ [Creative Commons Attribution](#)

▶ [Further Information and Resources](#)

Related

Individuals

• [Shane Maloney](#)

Projects

• [Active Region Classification and Flare Forecasting](#)

Processes

• [Activity Indicator: Solar Active Region Classification](#)

Page Suggestions & Support

[Provide feedback](#)

Figure 27 - ARCAFF Data Collection Solar Active Region Classification Details view

Figure 27 shows the overview of the ARCAFF Data Collection, which includes a section named “Access this Data Collection”. As it has an API assigned to it, users see a “Go to API” button. By clicking this button, the PeSC dynamically generates an interface within the PeSC, representing the details in the OpenAPI specification file, Figure 28. There, a user can interact with the Model, as shown in Figures 29 and 30.

Interact with Activity Indicator: Solar Active Region Classification via API

Activity Indicator: Solar Active Region Classification

ARCNET

<https://arcaff.sztaki.hun-ren.hu/openapi.json>

Active Region Classification and Flare Forecasting (ARCAFF) API

ARCAFF API

Active Region Classification and Flare Forecasting (ARCAFF) API

ARCNET

Active Region Classification Network (ARCNET) provides an API to AR classifications.

AR Cutout Classification

Given a AR magnetogram cutout return the classifications Hale (magnetic) and McIntosh (modified Zurich) classifications.

AR Detection

Given a full disk magnetogram return the bounding boxes and classification for each detected AR.

[ARCAFF - Website](#)

Start typing to filter sections...

AR Cutout Classification

Classify cutouts generated from a magnetogram at the given date and location.

Classify Cutout

Classify Cutout

Full disk AR Detection

Detect and classify all AR from a magnetogram for the given date.

Full Disk Detection

Full Disk Detection

Figure 28 - ARCAFF Data Collection Solar Active Region Classification API

Figure 29 demonstrates a sample API call to the “AR Cutout Classification” functionality where time, hgs_latitude, hgs_longitude were given as input parameters and the model returned a JSON object counting the location of the active region and the Hale and McIntosh classifications for this region in this particular case there was no AR and the model returned QS.

AR Cutout Classification

Classify cutouts generated from a magnetogram at the given date and location.

Classify Cutout

Classify a cutout generated from a magnetogram at the given date and location as URL parameters.

Parameters Cancel

Name	Description
time * required string(\$date-time) (query)	<input type="text" value="2024-01-01T00:00:00"/>
hgs_latitude * required number (query)	<input type="text" value="-70"/>
hgs_longitude * required number (query)	<input type="text" value="10"/>

[Run /arcnet/classify_cutout/](#) [Clear](#)

Responses

Details

```
{
  "time": "2024-01-01T00:00:00",
  "hgs_latitude": -70,
  "hgs_longitude": 10,
  "hale_class": "Q5",
  "mcintosh_class": "Q5"
}
```

[Download](#)

Figure 29 - ARCAFF Solar Active Region Classification - AR Cutout Classification Functionality

Figure 30 demonstrates a sample API call to the “Full disk AR Detection”, where time is the only input parameter. The Model returned a JSON object like the one in Figure 31. The JSON object contains the location and classification, Hale and McIntosh, for all detected AR on the disk at the given date.

Full disk AR Detection Detect and classify all AR from a magnetogram for the given date.

Full Disk Detection

Detect and classify all ARs in a magnetogram at the given date as a URL parameter.

Parameters Cancel

Name	Description
time <small>required</small> string(\$date-time) (query)	<input type="text" value="2024-01-01T00:00:00"/>

Run /arcnet/full_disk_detection Clear

Responses

Details

```
[
  {
    "time": "2024-01-01T00:00:00",
    "bbox": {
      "bottom_left": {
        "latitude": -25,
        "longitude": 61
      },
      "top_right": {
        "latitude": -15,
        "longitude": 71
      }
    },
    "hale_class": "Alpha",
    "mcintosh_class": "Hsx"
  },
  {
    "time": "2024-01-01T00:00:00",
    "bbox": {
      "bottom_left": {
        "latitude": 9,
```

Download

Figure 30 - ARCAFF Solar Active Region Classification - Full disk AR Detection Functionality


```
[
  {
    "time": "2024-01-01T00:00:00",
    "bbox": {
      "bottom_left": {
        "latitude": -25,
        "longitude": 61
      },
      "top_right": {
        "latitude": -15,
        "longitude": 71
      }
    },
    "hale_class": "Alpha",
    "mcintosh_class": "Hsx"
  },
  {
    "time": "2024-01-01T00:00:00",
    "bbox": {
      "bottom_left": {
        "latitude": 9,
        "longitude": 61
      },
      "top_right": {
        "latitude": 19,
        "longitude": 71
      }
    },
    "hale_class": "Beta",
    "mcintosh_class": "Cao"
  },
  {
    "time": "2024-01-01T00:00:00",
    "bbox": {
      "bottom_left": {
        "latitude": -18,
        "longitude": -20
      },
      "top_right": {
        "latitude": -8,
        "longitude": -10
      }
    },
    "hale_class": "Beta",
    "mcintosh_class": "Dao"
  }
]
```

Figure 31 - ARCAFF Solar Active Region Classification - Full disk AR Detection Functionality Results

3. Summary

This deliverable described the process of making an ARCAFF model publicly available from the PITHIA e-Science Centre. As the ARCAFF DL models are currently under development, a representative “mock” model has been developed that displays the same (or at least very similar) API as the final model. Therefore, the publication process was realistically demonstrated during this exercise.

The publication process started by creating a Docker image of the model and deploying it on the HUN-REN SZTAKI cloud. After that the model was deployed in the PITHIA e-Science Centre. This publication included the creation of an ARCAFF institution within the PeSC, the registration of users who will own the deployed models, the creation of several XML

registration files describing the scientific meaning of the published model, and finally the publication of the previously deployed API. Once published, the model execution was successfully tested in the eSC.

Based on this work, the full pipeline of deploying and publishing models has been successfully validated. Once the actual ARCAFF DL models are implemented and available, this validated process will be applied in each case.